

FAIRagro

FAIRagro Concept for Training, Education and Educational Resources

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I Table of Contents

I Table of Contents	1
II List of Abbreviations	3
1 Background	4
1.1 FAIRagro	4
1.1.1 FAIRagro’s Structure and Organisation	4
1.1.2 Training and Education in FAIRagro	5
1.2 RDM Training in Germany	6
1.2.1 Training on generic RDM topics	6
1.2.2 Learning Objectives of Training Programmes	8
1.3 Challenges of RDM in Agrosystems Research	8
1.3.1 Discipline-Specific Training for Agricultural Sciences.....	9
1.3.2 Offerings in Related Disciplines.....	10
1.4 RDM in Agricultural Science Education	12
1.4.1 Structured Doctoral Programmes for Agricultural Sciences and Related Disciplines in Germany.....	12
1.4.2 RDM in Structured Doctoral Programmes.....	13
1.4.3 Structured Training Programmes for Agricultural Science RDM	13
1.5 Conclusion	14
2 Objectives of FAIRagro’s Training and Educational Activities	14
3 Strategy.....	15
3.1 Target Groups	15
3.1.1 Researchers	15
3.1.2 Disseminators.....	16
3.2 Training Content.....	17
3.3 Training Team	19
3.4 Formats	19
3.5 Certification	22
3.6 Feedback	22
4 Measures	23
4.1 Training.....	23
4.1.1 University Partnerships	23

4.1.2 Cooperation With Other Partners	24
4.1.3 Workshops at Specialist Conferences.....	24
4.1.4 Training on FAIRagro Tools.....	25
4.1.5 Training on Request.....	25
4.2 Open Educational Resources.....	27
4.2.1 Gathering of Existing Discipline-Specific Resources.....	27
4.2.2 Provision of Training Materials for Individual Events.....	28
4.2.3 Provision of the Modular Training Module “RDM in Agrosystems Research”	28
4.2.4 Provision of the Modular Education module “RDM in Agrosystems Research” ...	29
4.2.5 Creation of Self-Study Materials	29
4.2.6 Publication	30
4.3 Education	31
4.3.1 Educational Activities within Structured Doctoral Programmes.....	31
4.3.2 Education in the Form of Certificate Courses.....	33
4.4 FAIRagro Portal.....	33
5 Outlook for the Second Funding Phase	34
6 References.....	35

II List of Abbreviations

ATB – Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (Leibniz-Institut für Agrartechnik und Bioökonomie e.V.)
BMBF – German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung)
CGIAR – Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research
DALIA – Data Literacy Alliance
de.NBI – German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure
DINI – German Initiative for Network Information (Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation e. V.)
DMP – Data Management Plan
DSSC – Data Steward Service Center
ECTS – European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
EOSC – European Open Science Cloud
FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAO – Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
gfbio – German Federation for Biological Data (Gesellschaft für Biologische Daten e.V.)
GODAN – Global Open Data for Agriculture & Nutrition
HeFDI – Hessian Research Data Infrastructures
IPK – Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (Leibniz-Institut für Pflanzengenetik und Kulturpflanzenforschung)
M – Measure
MOOC – Massive Open Online Course
NFDI – National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur)
OER – Open Educational Resources
RDA – Research Data Alliance
RDM – Research Data Management
SciWIn – Scientific Workflow Infrastructure
Stats4SD – Statistics for Sustainable Development
TA – Task Area
TH – University of Applied Sciences (Technische Hochschule)
TUM – Technical University of Munich (Technische Universität München)
UC – Use Case
WG – Working Group
ZALF – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung)

1 Background

1.1 FAIRagro

Agrosystems research plays a vital role in addressing key agricultural objectives, such as reducing pesticide and fertiliser use, promoting soil carbon enrichment, and enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services. Achieving these goals relies on the integration of a wide range of disciplines, including genetics, plant breeding, crop science, soil science, and geosciences. Each discipline includes its own set of research methods, such as monitoring and experimentation, data analysis and modelling, or synthesis and visualisation. Given the diversity of disciplines, data types, and formats encompassed by agrosystems research, conducting interdisciplinary data analysis is no easy task. Notable challenges in research data management (RDM) in this context include the heterogeneity of RDM standards across disciplines and sub-disciplines, limited interoperability between existing domain-specific and institutional repositories, a lack of standards for managing sensitive data (e.g. from private farms) and the uncertainty this creates, the involvement of various data owners, and the absence of consistent standards for assessing and describing data quality (1).

Launched in March 2023, FAIRagro is a consortium within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) that unites 32 institutions (11 co-applicant organisations and 21 participants) from across agrosystems research and infrastructure. Its mission is to establish a collaborative RDM approach in Germany that spans a diverse range of disciplines, scales and methodologies. FAIRagro will support researchers, students and infrastructure providers in managing their data transparently and sustainably throughout the research data lifecycle while fostering a cultural shift towards FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and collaborative RDM (2). To enable interdisciplinary collaboration in agrosystems research, FAIRagro is developing tailored tools, policies and best practices designed to be embedded within the research community. Achieving these objectives will require a cultural change in the relevant community (1).

1.1.1 FAIRagro's Structure and Organisation

FAIRagro is organised into five task areas (TAs; see Figure 1). TA5 oversees the management and coordination of the consortium, while TA1 is responsible for organising FAIRagro's use cases (UCs), with the initial phase featuring six UCs addressing the topics of breeding, agronomy, pests and diseases, long-term experiments, Farming 4.0 and crop modelling. As FAIRagro progresses through its operational phase, additional use cases from fields such as animal husbandry and forestry are planned. TA3 focuses on developing solutions for standardisation, interoperability and data quality, which are essential for enabling the reuse, quality control and annotation of research data. Building on the requirements identified in TA1 and the standards established by TA3, TA4 implements the necessary

components and infrastructure services for federated RDM along the FAIR data lifecycle and develops technical solutions and services.

Figure 1: Structure of the FAIRagro task areas

TA2 Community Involvement and Networking is dedicated to raising awareness of FAIR RDM practices and increasing both knowledge of and engagement with FAIRagro’s outcomes and services among researchers. To boost acceptance of new structures, standards and tools within the scientific community, there is a strong emphasis on understanding researchers’ needs and the realities of their work. Five measures (M) are employed for this purpose: M 2.1 Communication and Dissemination organises roadshows and community summits and operates the FAIRagro portal as a central point of contact for RDM in agrosystems research; M 2.2 Community Participation focuses on systematically collecting feedback from the community; M 2.3 Use Case Onboarding establishes and develops onboarding processes for new use cases; M 2.4 Training and Education develops tailored training courses and materials to strengthen RDM skills; and M 2.5 Data Steward Service Center (DSSC) acts as a central hub for RDM expertise, bringing together five data stewards with specialised knowledge across different data types and domains (1).

1.1.2 Training and Education in FAIRagro

M 2.4 Training and Education is responsible for coordinating and delivering training and educational activities. This measure has various resources at its disposal: 1) Training – time-limited professional development programmes designed to be completed alongside regular work commitments; 2) Education – learning that takes place in an academic setting as preparation for working in the profession (often more comprehensive than training) (3); 3) Open educational resources (OER) – freely licensed learning and teaching materials that support self-paced learning for individuals and can be reused or adapted by educators.

The success of M 2.4 relies on close collaboration with the DSSC data stewards, who themselves work in scientific fields and act as a bridge between scientific research and infrastructure, as well as with researchers from the UCs and staff from TA3 and TA4 who are responsible for developing the services and tools that FAIRagro provides to the community (1).

1.2 RDM Training in Germany

Many locations across Germany are pursuing advances in research data management. These include RDM state initiatives and local networks in twelve federal states, as well as the NFDI with its 26 discipline-specific consortia (4, 5). In addition, most universities and research institutes have their own RDM service centres (5). Many of these institutions offer RDM training programmes and courses in various formats. Participants in these courses connect with each other at various levels. Within the NFDI, the Training and Education Section (EduTrain) is engaged in cross-consortia work on topics including material inventories, development of a modular scalable concept, development of a knowledge base in cooperation with the knowledge graph of the Data Literacy Alliance (DALIA), development of certified training formats, networking and outreach (6, 7). The Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group of the DINI/nestor WG Research Data serves as another important network (8).

1.2.1 Training on generic RDM topics

Training Offerings

Training in the general principles of RDM is provided by various university and institutional RDM centres in Germany, as well as through RDM initiatives at the state level. These offerings vary in terms of target audience and scope. For instance, Saxony's RDM Initiative saxFDM provides a modular introduction to the fundamentals of RDM (9). The programme run by the DINI/nestor Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group delivers specialised training courses on key RDM topics such as data documentation and legal aspects, which are also published as open educational resources (OER) (10–12). The University of Bremen's Data Train programme – established by the U Bremen Research Alliance – provides a comprehensive modular training curriculum for doctoral students. This includes a series of workshops on RDM basics alongside a further workshop series that alternates each year between the Data Scientist and Data Steward programmes. Participants can choose to attend individual sessions or complete the entire module (13). The hessian RDM initiative (Hessian Research Data Infrastructures – HeFDI) offers an extensive training programme through its Data School, featuring both foundational and advanced modules tailored for doctoral students and research staff (14).

In addition to in-person training, a wide array of online self-learning resources and recorded training sessions are available. Massive open online courses (MOOCs) provide free access to in-depth online training programmes designed to accommodate large numbers

of participants. For example, the University of Edinburgh offers the MANTRA MOOC, which covers general RDM topics and can be customised for students, researchers, senior academics or information professionals (i.e. disseminators) (15). This course has already been adapted by several German universities (16). Further MOOCs are available at the European level, including the Data Steward training course created by FAIRsFAIR and the European Open Science Cloud's EOSC Synergy project, which is aimed at professionals working in research data support roles (17). HeFDI has developed a self-learning MOOC module on RDM for students, doctoral candidates and researchers. This module is designed for reuse and is already being adapted by universities and integrated into their curricula (18–21). By incorporating the HeFDI online self-learning module into academic programmes, universities are helping to advance education in this field. Moreover, like most online learning resources on Open Science and RDM, the HeFDI module is freely available under an OER license (18).

Educational Offerings

In Germany, several universities and higher education institutions offer Bachelor's and Master's degree programmes in information science and data management, in which research data management is included as a key component of the curriculum (22). Additionally, a number of certificate courses are available for students and graduates from other disciplines, as well as for further target groups such as library staff, specialists and managers involved in research data-related activities (22). For instance, FDM Brandenburg provides a comprehensive certificate course on the general principles of RDM for Bachelor's and Master's students from various degree programmes. This course spans five full days and earns students two to four European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits (23). A ten-month certificate course in Research Data Management is offered by TH Köln – University of Applied Sciences in collaboration with ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences and the North Rhine-Westphalian RDM initiative *fdm.nrw*. Upon successful completion of an examination, participants earn eight ECTS credits for this course (24). TH Köln also offers a specialised Data Librarian certificate course tailored to employees of scientific libraries (25). The initial phase of the RDMTraining4NFDI basic service features a workshop series and summer school aimed at data stewards and RDM trainers (26).

Open Educational Resources

Many training events are subsequently made available as OER, typically in the form of a video recording or presentation slides. In some cases, the OER may include supplementary materials such as exercise sheets or surveys that are integrated into the course. Training scripts, however, are rarely included (10–12). Online self-learning courses are frequently offered as OER, enabling them to be adapted and incorporated into institutions' in-house infrastructures (18, 27). Additionally, a variety of other resources, such as RDM games and videos, are available under open licences (28, 29). Some providers curate collections of open training materials. A well-known example in Germany is the collection of resources provided by the DINI/nestor Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group (30). At the European level, the EOSC Pillar serves as a central repository for training resources (31). A

wide range of materials on RDM topics can also be accessed through the OERSI search index for open educational resources in higher education. This platform allows users to filter searches by subject area, resource type, language and licence (32). DALIA is developing a knowledge graph for the NFDI, which will serve as a central platform for sharing and accessing OER within the NFDI environment (33).

1.2.2 Learning Objectives of Training Programmes

As part of the European project “Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe”, a handbook has been created to support the integration of FAIR content into curricula and teaching at higher education institutions (34). Based on this handbook, the DINI/nestor WG Research Data has developed a learning objective matrix tailored to the target groups of Bachelor’s, Master’s, and PhD students, as well as Data Stewards. The aim is to establish standards for topic areas and target group-specific learning objectives within RDM training programmes and courses (35). This matrix has already been adapted by several NFDI consortia to reflect their specific areas of expertise (36). Additionally, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) has introduced a train-the-trainer programme as part of its FDMentor project, designed to prepare new trainers in the field of research data management. This two-day workshop combines didactic methods with RDM topics and is regularly offered by organisations such as FDM.nrw and saxFDM. The programme concept is also available as OER (37). A customised version of the programme has already been developed for the field of psychology (38).

1.3 Challenges of RDM in Agrosystems Research

The wide range of research questions and sub-disciplines within agricultural sciences and agrosystems research results in a highly diverse array of data, requiring tailored RDM approaches. While numerical data constitutes the bulk of agricultural research outputs, other types of data – such as text, images, geodata, source code, video and audio – are also commonly produced. These datasets often include time series, laboratory measurements, weather records, and geographical references, all of which must be carefully considered during data processing and publication. The annual volume of data generated per researcher varies greatly, from as little as 1 GB to over 10 TB (39).

Agrosystems research covers a variety of scales, ranging from genes and individual plants to fields, farms and entire landscapes. The six initial FAIRagro use cases reflect key research questions and workflows within agrosystems research, with each UC addressing a different scale (1). These UCs generate diverse types of data, including tabular experimental and simulation data, raw genetic sequences, LiDAR data (large-scale point clouds), multidimensional images, and (multi-)spectral data across various domains (e.g. plant genetics: single nucleotide polymorphisms, species, breeding). Other examples of generated data include soil data, weather time series, crop management records, land use information, farm operations data, market trends, harvest losses, monitoring of natural enemies, and pest and disease surveillance. This broad variety of data types provides a

valuable foundation for developing RDM measures, but its heterogeneity is a key challenge for RDM in agrosystems research, alongside issues such as data ownership and the handling of personal data (e.g., from private farms). Additionally, much of the data is collected in the field under conditions where electricity and internet access may be unreliable. Geographical and meteorological factors also influence how data is gathered.

Publishing research data and adhering to FAIR principles is not yet standard practice among agricultural science data producers. Many researchers recognise that their datasets could be profitably reused by others, yet awareness of existing RDM standards and best practices remains limited (39). Building this knowledge and expertise within the community is therefore a key objective of targeted RDM training programmes tailored to agrosystems research.

1.3.1 Discipline-Specific Training for Agricultural Sciences

Discipline-specific RDM training programmes introduce not only general concepts but also the specialised tools and services required to handle the data types used within the field. These programmes also focus on infrastructures and standards relevant to the discipline, incorporating examples and exercises tailored to common research questions. This approach highlights the relevance of the training to learners' academic lives, fostering intrinsic motivation and increasing the likelihood that the knowledge will be applied in practice (3).

Training Offerings

Across Germany, there are 11 universities with agricultural science faculties (40) and 14 universities of applied sciences specialising in agricultural sciences. Most of these institutions have a centre, department or team dedicated to RDM. While many universities offer training sessions on various aspects of RDM, these are often generic in nature. For example, the Technical University of Munich (TUM) provides basic RDM training for undergraduate and postgraduate students, doctoral candidates and researchers. However, TUM also offers a semester-long Data Steward Training module specifically for doctoral candidates and researchers from various disciplines. This module addresses not only general RDM topics but also solutions to discipline-specific RDM challenges (41). Some universities also provide discipline-specific materials and training outside agricultural sciences (e.g. for medical and biomedical sciences in collaboration with ZB MED) (42). Humboldt University Berlin ran a one-off workshop on Research Data Management for Agricultural Scientists and Biologists in collaboration with the RDM Forum on Biodiversity, Ecology And Environmental Research at the Society for Biological Data e.V. (gfbio) (43). This two-hour session covered RDM fundamentals with a focus on aspects relevant to agricultural sciences and biology (44). The presentation of this event was made available as OER (45). However, specialised training tailored specifically to agricultural sciences or related disciplines is not offered on a regular basis at any of these institutions. None of the 25 agricultural science universities currently provides an RDM training programme explicitly tailored to agricultural sciences or agrosystems research.

Nonetheless, other agrosystems research institutions do offer discipline-specific RDM training. For example, the Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) has conducted several workshops on RDM topics and made the presentation slides available as OER (46–48). Similarly, the Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK) has run various in-house RDM training sessions (49). These workshops often combine general RDM content with an in-depth introduction to the institution's own RDM services.

Internationally, some agricultural science organisations have developed online self-paced courses, videos and webinars on RDM in the agricultural context, some of which are available as OER. For instance, the Data Management Support Pack created by the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) provides a collection of texts, templates and videos covering various aspects of RDM tailored to the specific target groups of Principle Investigator, Researcher or Data Manager (50). The United States Department of Agriculture offers webinars on topics such as publishing data in Ag Data Commons, creating Data Management Plans (DMPs), using data dictionaries, and generating machine-readable data; recordings of these webinars are publicly available (51). In collaboration with the Collaborative Crop Research Program (CCRP) of the McKnight Foundation, Stats4SD (Statistics for Sustainable Development) offers a four-module video course on the topics of Data Management Concepts, Data Management in Practice, Data Management in R, and Qualitative Data Management (52). A primarily text-based MOOC on Open Data Management in Agriculture and Nutrition was created in 2017 by Global Open Data for Agriculture & Nutrition (GODAN) and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (53).

Open Educational Resources

The MOOCs developed by GODAN and FAO are available under an open licence (CC BY SA), allowing learners to access them freely and enabling educators to adapt and reuse them as needed (54, 55). Video recordings of webinars (e.g. by Ag Data Commons (51)) and short videos (e.g. by FAO Knowledge Sharing (56)) are also freely accessible under open licences. Presentation slides from past training sessions are available for trainers to reuse in their own workshops (45–48). However, additional materials for training sessions such as scripts, exercise guides or collections of links are rarely included with these resources (49).

1.3.2 Offerings in Related Disciplines

Some disciplines related to agrosystems research have already established an RDM training infrastructure. In **bioinformatics**, for example, the Training Platform run by ELIXIR Europe connects trainers from various countries (57). At the national level, the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI) collaborates with multiple partners to offer training in various disciplines, including RDM (58). Many of de.NBI's offerings are also relevant to sub-disciplines within agrosystems research. One of its key training partners is the IPK, which coordinates the German Crop BioGreenformatics Network. This network provides crop plant-related bioinformatics services and training programmes focused on plant breeding (59). The Carpentries – a global initiative that teaches foundational computational

and data science skills (60) – offers tailored Data Carpentry workshops on the analysis and management of genomics data. Their curriculum also includes accredited Data Carpentry workshops on geospatial data and ecology datasets (61).

RDM training programmes and OER for **geospatial data** are provided by several organisations, including the Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences (GFZ), the Institute of Meteorology at Freie Universität Berlin, the European Geoscience Union and the University of California. These resources include online courses (62, 63), recorded training sessions (64), and supplementary materials such as handbooks (65).

In the field of **earth system sciences**, the NFDI consortium NFDI4Earth has developed the NFDI4Earth Academy to provide and promote training, networking and collaborative research for doctoral students and postdocs. Participants embark on a two-year programme with a peer-mentoring focus that flexibly caters to learners' needs (66). In addition to this educational offering, NFDI4Earth is establishing a network of partners who offer RDM education and training tailored specifically to earth system sciences. It also publishes training materials as OER, which are made centrally accessible through its Educational Portal (67).

The NFDI4Biodiversity consortium organises seasonal schools for early-career researchers working in **biodiversity and environmental sciences**. It also hosts workshops on NFDI4Biodiversity tools and services as well as legal aspects and makes recordings available as OER (68). Additionally, NFDI4Biodiversity has adapted HeFDI's online self-learning module on RDM (see 1.2.1) to focus specifically on the management of biodiversity data. This module is accessible under an open licence (69).

The Helmholtz Information & Data Science Academy provides a wide range of training programmes across various fields of research, including earth and environmental sciences (70).

DATAplant, the NFDI consortium for **fundamental plant research**, is developing a comprehensive collection of modular teaching resources as OER, including short text segments and individual presentation slides (“bricks”), which can be organised along didactic paths into thematic units that cover complete topics or concepts. These units can then be used to create events (“disseminations”) or series of events tailored to specific learning environments and target audiences (71).

1.4 RDM in Agricultural Science Education

1.4.1 Structured Doctoral Programmes for Agricultural Sciences and Related Disciplines in Germany

As of December 2024, 26 structured doctoral programmes were identified in Germany that specifically target PhD students in agricultural sciences and/or related disciplines. These programmes are highly heterogeneous in structure (72).

The Technical University of Munich and the universities of Bonn, Giessen, Kassel, Hohenheim and Göttingen offer doctoral study programmes (73–75) or university graduate schools (76–81) tailored to PhD students at their respective institutions (72). Some of these subject-specific programmes cover a broader range of life sciences fields, such as those offered by the Bonn International Graduate School – Land and Food and by TUM (76–78), while others are aimed at PhD students in specific disciplines, such as agricultural sciences (e.g. the doctoral study programmes in agricultural sciences at the universities of Hohenheim and Göttingen), agricultural economics (e.g. the International PhD Program for Agricultural Economics, Bioeconomy and Sustainable Food Systems at the University of Giessen) or forestry (e.g., the PhD Programme in Forest Sciences and Forest Ecology at the University of Göttingen) (73–75, 80). Two of these graduate schools – at the University of Bonn and the University of Kassel – have a strong international orientation and adopt an interdisciplinary approach that caters to agricultural scientists as well as researchers in development and social sciences (79, 81).

Doctoral students in the field of agricultural economics also have the option of the Doctoral Certificate Program in Agricultural Economics, a discipline-specific programme offered collaboratively by several German-speaking universities and the Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) (82).

Other non-university research institutions, such as the IPK, the Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB), the Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, and the Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies, offer structured programmes to all PhD students at their institutes. These are either provided in cooperation with universities (83) or complement other postgraduate programmes (84–86), offering comprehensive and targeted support tailored to doctoral candidates' needs. Similar programmes exist for larger collaborative research centres (e.g. Collaborative Research Centre CRC1502 DETECT) and excellence clusters (e.g. PhenoRob) (87, 88).

Research Training Groups with narrowly focused research questions and a limited number of fixed doctoral positions bring together teams of researchers from various national and international universities and research institutions (72). These groups may adopt either an interdisciplinary focus (88–90) or a highly discipline-specific approach (87, 91–98), with the

latter including topics such as agricultural and forestry sciences, plant science, plant breeding, agricultural economics and remote sensing.

These postgraduate programmes show considerable diversity in their structural and conceptual design. Some offer module handbooks with a broad range of mandatory and elective modules specifically designed for PhD students (73–77, 82, 93, 98). Others offer only a few specialised modules which are supplemented by general content from other graduate schools (84–87, 90, 91) and/or allow their PhD students to enrol in courses from Bachelor's or Master's degree programmes within their own faculty (78, 90).

The scope of these programmes and the documentation of required achievements also vary significantly. Some programmes only provide optional resources such as courses, lectures and OER (81, 86). Other programmes have mandatory components, such as compulsory events or courses, and may require students to complete a set number of semester hours for elective activities (78, 83). However, most programmes use a credit system (e.g. ECTS) to track completed work in mandatory and elective modules. The total number of credits required varies between 15 (76, 88) and 30 (79, 82, 98). Activities such as supervising or teaching responsibilities, presenting one's work at academic conferences, or contributing to funding proposals are sometimes integrated into the credit system but are occasionally required without earning credits. However, the specific structure and requirements are not publicly disclosed for all programmes.

1.4.2 RDM in Structured Doctoral Programmes

The integration of RDM competencies within structured doctoral programmes is as varied and diverse as the programmes themselves. Among the 26 identified doctoral programmes, 18 incorporate RDM training in various forms. Often, specific aspects of RDM are included within compulsory (98) or elective modules (79, 82, 91, 95, 97) on good scientific practice or academic skills. Nine programmes offer elective modules specifically dedicated to RDM (76–78, 80, 87, 88, 90, 94, 96), while two feature compulsory modules covering this topic (89, 93). The scope and content of these offerings vary widely, however. For instance, module durations range from brief two-hour workshops (78) to semester-long modules worth 2–3 ECTS credits (76, 93). Some sessions are integral and permanent components of the curriculum (78, 89, 93), whereas others are one-off events (87, 94, 96).

1.4.3 Structured Training Programmes for Agricultural Science RDM

Germany does not have standalone training programmes specifically tailored to RDM in agricultural sciences. At the European level, the EnTrust network is providing a training programme for eleven doctoral candidates focused on agricultural data management as part of the Next Generation of Trustworthy Agri-Data Management project. However, its emphasis is not on research data, but rather on fostering close collaboration with industry partners (54, 55). Internationally, several universities – primarily in the US – offer certificate courses in agricultural data science that focus predominantly on data analysis and processing (99–101).

1.5 Conclusion

Germany has a broad and established network of training courses focused on general RDM principles. These programmes serve diverse target groups, with most targeting researchers – particularly doctoral students and early-career academics. However, training opportunities for disseminators remain comparatively limited.

At the national level, there are very few examples of RDM training specifically tailored to the needs of agrosystems researchers. Many of these discipline-specific programmes concentrate on specific services offered by the providers. Internationally, some discipline-specific courses exist, often emphasising open data and targeting users or providers of agricultural data that do not explicitly qualify as research data. While some resources are available as OER, their quality is inconsistent and they may not be sufficiently up to date. Many consist only of webinar recordings or presentation slides and lack supplementary materials such as teaching scripts or exercises, which limits their usefulness for educators.

RDM is occasionally included in agricultural training for early-career researchers, but its scope and quality vary greatly, and it is frequently presented as a secondary topic within other modules. Comprehensive training in data management skills is not yet widespread in agricultural education; in some cases, these skills are either not taught at all or are only offered through brief elective modules targeted at doctoral students who are already interested in the subject.

Existing live training sessions, online self-learning courses, and other training materials are available from various organisations; however, there is no centralised platform where learners can find information about offerings specifically aimed at agricultural scientists. FAIRagro's mission to create a well-structured concept for training and education in agriculture-specific FAIR research data management therefore addresses an important gap.

2 Objectives of FAIRagro's Training and Educational Activities

The training activities conducted by FAIRagro serve as a key instrument for strengthening awareness of the importance of effective and FAIR RDM within the agrosystems research community and for fostering a cultural shift. These activities aim to fill the gap in comprehensive training that is specifically tailored to agrosystems research and its various sub-disciplines at the national level. To achieve this, FAIRagro pursues three main objectives:

- 1) Equip researchers with both general and discipline-specific RDM knowledge and skills that can be directly applied in their daily work.
- 2) Provide training on guidelines, standards, tools and services developed by FAIRagro in order to:

- a) demonstrate the benefits of their use for disseminators;
 - b) facilitate integration into daily workflows;
 - c) gather direct feedback and gain insights into community needs.
- 3) Ensure the sustainable adoption of RDM practices within the agrosystems research community by recruiting disseminators and empowering them – even beyond FAIRagro’s funding period – to
- a) deliver discipline-specific RDM training for researchers at their institutions; and/or
 - b) integrate RDM into agricultural science education programmes.

3 Strategy

To achieve these objectives, FAIRagro has identified different target groups, each of which will be addressed through tailored approaches. A modular training programme and educational course, "RDM in Agrosystems Research", will be developed, which can be specifically adapted to each target group and to the context in which training is delivered.

3.1 Target Groups

The target groups for FAIRagro’s training activities are defined on two different levels: first, the sub-discipline of agrosystems research and the types of data they work with; and, second, the two distinct roles of

- researchers, and
- disseminators.

Overall, FAIRagro’s focus is on individuals based in Germany, though the option of using our services on an international level has not been excluded.

3.1.1 Researchers

Researchers may act as both data producers and data users. In both roles, RDM practices and skills should be embedded into their daily workflows in order to generate FAIR research data that can be efficiently reused. This group can be further divided by career stage into early-career researchers (doctoral students, postdocs) and senior researchers.

Early-career researchers are at the beginning of their academic careers, working on their first projects that involve the large-scale production and use of research data. Unlike students, they already have access to established scientific methodologies (102). Integrating RDM skills into their scientific practice from the outset is essential, making early-career researchers the primary target group for RDM training. They can be reached through: 1) affiliated institutions, particularly agricultural science universities; 2) professional networks such as de.NBI, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Biodiversity, DataPLANT and FAIRagro’s own participants and co-applicants; and 3) academic conferences. Training

offered via these channels should clearly emphasise the relevance of RDM to their research and build competency in RDM techniques. Offerings will include both introductory courses that provide discipline-specific RDM foundations and advanced sessions that offer deeper insights into specialised aspects of RDM.

In addition to scheduled training, OER will be provided to support self-paced, needs-driven learning. Early-career researchers, particularly doctoral students, are also the focus of FAIRagro's educational efforts to integrate RDM into graduate school curricula.

Senior researchers bring years of experience in processing, generating and utilising research data. While many possess basic RDM knowledge and skills, awareness of data FAIRification is not universal. This group is an important target for RDM training as they serve both as data providers/users and as disseminators who supervise junior researchers and share data handling techniques. There are two main challenges in reaching this group: first, they are unlikely to be motivated to change tried-and-tested practices without a clear demonstration of how FAIR RDM will benefit their daily work and career progression; second, their time is limited, so training sessions must deliver relevant content efficiently to ensure their participation. The most effective approach for this audience is short, focused sessions that highlight specific aspects of RDM, along with tools and services developed through FAIRagro.

Academic conferences in the field of agrosystems research serve as key access points for training this group. The specialised focus of these conferences allows targeted engagement with researchers from sub-disciplines of agrosystems research, enabling content to be tailored to the realities of their day-to-day work. Furthermore, all training designed for early-career researchers will also be open to researchers at any career stage, ensuring broad access to professional development opportunities and fostering knowledge exchange.

3.1.2 Disseminators

Disseminators comprise senior researchers, data stewards and staff members from infrastructure institutions such as libraries, computing centres and research departments at universities and non-university research institutions.

Staff at infrastructure institutions include RDM coordinators at universities with agricultural science faculties. RDM coordinators are often affiliated with university libraries, IT centres or other university departments. They possess comprehensive knowledge of research data management, which they make available to researchers and students. They also occasionally offer training on general RDM topics, for instance at the University of Bonn, Humboldt University Berlin and Kiel University (42, 103, 104). However, RDM coordinators typically lack discipline-specific knowledge.

University libraries with agricultural science faculties employ subject librarians who are responsible (either exclusively or alongside other subjects) for agricultural sciences. These

specialists advise students and researchers who work in this subject area. Since RDM is rarely one of their core responsibilities, it can be assumed that prior knowledge of RDM varies considerably within this target group.

Academic staff at universities with an agricultural science focus serve as access points for integrating RDM into university teaching. This is vital for providing students with a basic understanding of the fundamental principles of RDM. FAIRagro raises lecturers' awareness of the need to integrate RDM into teaching and supports the conceptual work required for curriculum integration, enabling sustainable implementation despite potential resource constraints among academic staff. Additionally, OER resources are made accessible to allow lecturers to deliver discipline-specific RDM teaching with minimal preparation.

Data stewards bridge the gap between infrastructure and research. With a robust knowledge of research data management in their particular field, they advise and train researchers in effective data management practices. Data stewards are either qualified information scientists who must familiarise themselves with discipline-specific requirements or agricultural science professionals who must develop data literacy and RDM skills (22). The key challenge for this group is enhancing the pedagogical skills required to effectively transmit RDM knowledge to researchers.

FAIRagro will support disseminators in offering discipline-specific RDM training by making OER findable and available for integration into their own courses. All FAIRagro training materials will be made available under an open licence, making it easy for disseminators to adapt them for different target groups. Other offerings will include pilot discipline-specific RDM training for disseminators with a focus on pedagogical skill development.

3.2 Training Content

To effectively address the needs of diverse target audiences, a modular training concept will be developed using a flexible 'building-block' approach. To tailor the training to different qualification levels (early-career researchers and data stewards), the first step is to adapt the RDM learning objective matrix to agrosystems research (35). This matrix outlines target group-specific learning objectives across the following key aspects of RDM: basics and overarching concepts; working with data; documentation and metadata; long-term preservation, publication, reuse; law and ethics; and supporting structures.

Existing OER, such as training materials from ZB MED (105), will serve as the foundation for general/core content. These materials will be enhanced with discipline-specific resources tailored to agrosystems research, as well as an introduction to tools and services provided by FAIRagro. The training programmes can be adapted to specific target audiences within one or more sub-disciplines of agrosystems research, such as soil science, phenotyping, genotyping and (big) geodata. For each of these sub-disciplines and their associated research data, key aspects of RDM will be identified together with the tools and standards that are either well-established or available in the field. Particular emphasis will be placed on tools and services offered by collaboration partners (e.g.

universities or other research institutions) as well as on the policies, best practices, services and tools developed by FAIRagro. Furthermore, solutions and implementations from FAIRagro's UCs will be incorporated into the training, covering topics such as data curation, data quality criteria, data integration and data harmonisation. The content for these sessions will primarily be developed by FAIRagro data stewards and/or subject matter experts from the UCs, TA3 or TA4. The coordination team will oversee the didactic preparation of the training materials.

RDM topics covered in the training programmes will include:

Fundamental Concepts

- Research data
- Definition of research data management
- Data documentation
 - Metadata and metadata standards
- FAIR principles
- Good scientific practice
- Policies and guidelines

Research Data Lifecycle

- Planning
 - Data management plans
- Data collection
 - Discipline-specific methods
 - Electronic lab notebooks
 - Electronic field notebooks and field experiment management systems
- Data storage and processing
 - Data organisation
 - Naming conventions
 - Folder structures
 - Versioning
 - File formats
 - Reproducible data analysis
 - SciWIn
- Data publishing
 - Collaboration tools
 - Persistent identifiers (PIDs)
 - Data repositories
- Data search and reuse
 - Services for data search
 - FAIRagro search service

Legal Aspects

- Data rights
 - Copyright
 - Licences

- Data protection
- Trade secrets

This range of topics can be expanded as needed. As the FAIRagro UCs are extended to include new sub-disciplines (forestry, animal breeding), the thematic scope will be re-evaluated and supplemented with additional content. Needs assessments will be conducted to ensure the training offered is tailored to the community's needs.

In collaboration with M 2.2, questions will be formulated to assess demand for potential training content and gauge the acceptability of various formats (self-study units, lectures, exercises, synchronous training – whether virtual or physical). These questions will be incorporated into training evaluations, ensuring continuous feedback on evolving needs. Additionally, queries submitted to the DSSC via the helpdesk will be regularly analysed to identify thematic priorities. In collaboration with M 2.5, surveys will be carried out at professional conferences and similar in-person events to get feedback on what the community needs from DSSC services, including training needs. Valuable insights into the content sought by the community can also be gained from both external and internal requests for training.

Frequently recurring topics will be assessed to determine whether they can be covered by dedicated training sessions or by providing self-study materials in the form of OER.

3.3 Training Team

For each training programme, a suitable team of FAIRagro trainers will be assembled. These subject-matter experts will co-teach courses tailored to the target audience, considering the types of data the participants use, the sub-disciplines they work in, and the chosen RDM aspects. The data stewards at FAIRagro's Data Steward Service Center (DSSC) are central to this effort. The five data stewards possess expertise in soil science, phenotyping, genotyping (big) geospatial data and legal aspects (106). They also have regular contact with the agricultural science community through the FAIRagro helpdesk and understand the community's RDM needs. Additional expertise can be sought from UC staff, who can provide highly specialised input to participants working on research questions similar to those addressed in the respective UCs. For training programmes that focus on specific sub-aspects of RDM – or that are explicitly designed to present FAIRagro tools and services – it is important to involve staff from TA3 and TA4, who can provide in-depth technical expertise and insights into specific topics and are responsible for developing FAIRagro tools and services.

3.4 Formats

FAIRagro training programmes offer varying levels of content:

- I. Comprehensive introduction to discipline-specific RDM

- II. In-depth discipline-specific exploration of individual RDM topics
- III. Introduction to specific FAIRagro tools or services

The format and scope of each training programme should reflect the context, learning content and target group in each case.

- 1) Type I or II training programmes that involve participants from various sub-disciplines of agrosystems research can vary in duration (ranging from a few hours to one or more half-days) and may be conducted either online or in person. The training can be divided into different sections to ensure participants receive tailored content despite their diverse backgrounds. The first part of the programme could provide a general overview of fundamental RDM concepts, after which participants can be asked to choose one or more topics that they would like to explore in greater depth. Follow-up workshops can then be offered for the most popular topics.
- 2) Type I or II training programmes that are aimed at a highly specialised target audience (e.g. doctoral students within a research project or institute) can be specifically tailored to the tools and services that are most relevant to the audience, as well as to their respective sub-discipline and the types of data they use. A hybrid approach may be employed, delivering introductory content online in advance, followed by a more hands-on, in-depth exploration of specific tools and services.
- 3) Training designed for conferences could, for example, involve short type I or type III in-person training sessions of 1–2 hours each. Workshop participants could be encouraged to bring laptops (depending on available space and prior communication with participants) so that they can try out FAIRagro's tools and services during the workshop. This direct interaction with users provides an opportunity to gather feedback on the practical application and user-friendliness of the tools, which can then be reviewed by the coordinators responsible for the measure.
- 4) Type III training programmes can be delivered in the form of short online sessions. Each session could present and demonstrate a particular tool before allowing participants to try it out for themselves and get answers to any technical or content-related questions from the other participants or trainers. The first part of each session could be recorded and made available as OER.

In all formats, participants should be actively engaged in order to meet the following objectives:

- A. Learners construct knowledge and skills through the self-directed discovery and application of knowledge based on constructivist learning theory (107).
- B. Trainers receive direct feedback on the participants' levels of knowledge/ability, interests, motivation, and how closely the learning aligns with their research/work routines.

- C. Participants can share their own experiences and best practices to foster peer learning and encourage a better understanding of other stakeholders' perspectives (e.g. data providers vs. users).
- D. Concentration is maintained through the use of varied activities (listening, reading, discussing, writing, researching, and problem-solving).

Various methods of engagement should be used to achieve these objectives. The exact tools used may differ depending on whether the training is online or face to face (Table 1).

Table 1: Engagement methods for online and in-person training

Method	Tools	Purpose	Objectives
Short surveys	Miro boards (108), Mentimeter (109)	Assess participants' knowledge, interests and motivation	B, C
Short quizzes	Miro boards (108), Mentimeter (109), Wheel of Fortune, etc.	Check if individual users can explain learned concepts and transfer them to other contexts	A, B, D
Word clouds, etc.	Miro boards (108), Mentimeter (109)	Collaborative brainstorming	B, C, D
Longer hands- on exercises	Breakout rooms (online)	Active application of learned concepts using practical examples, either individually or in small groups	A, B, C, D
Independent content research	Collection of links, documents	Discover, categorise and present the provided resources, services and tools, either individually or in small groups	A, C, D
Active coffee break	Suggested topics for discussion, coffee	Opportunity for participants to share experiences at in-person events	A, C, D

3.5 Certification

Attendance certificates serve as useful incentives for participation even in the case of short workshops without formal assessment components. Certification options should therefore be evaluated for all the training and educational activities we offer. This evaluation will draw on the certification structures being developed by RDMTraining4NFDI for the NFDI (26).

3.6 Feedback

To continuously enhance the quality of training programmes, feedback will be collected, analysed and utilised to improve future sessions. This process will be carried out on multiple levels.

Following each training session, the training team will conduct a short debriefing session to discuss the effectiveness of the training and opportunities for improvement. In this wrap-up discussion, the trainers will offer their perspective on how valuable the training was for the participants and reflect on their own role, thereby ensuring that facilitators from the various backgrounds (DSSC, UC, TA3, TA4 or collaboration partners) are able to do the best job of conveying their specialist knowledge.

Training sessions provide FAIRagro with vital community engagement opportunities. Gathering participant feedback is therefore particularly important. Working in conjunction with M 2.2, an evaluation tool is being developed to collect feedback on the content and format of the training and obtain information on the participants. This approach serves the dual purpose of improving current offerings whilst identifying future training needs within the community.

4 Measures

4.1 Training

By the end of 2027, FAIRagro will have delivered at least 33 virtual or in-person training programmes (see Figure 2).

4.1.1 University Partnerships

Training will be offered to staff at universities and higher education institutions specializing in agricultural sciences. To facilitate this, FAIRagro is actively collaborating with the RDM centres at these institutions, drawing on the successful model of discipline-specific RDM training established by ZB MED in partnership with NFDI4Health and NFDI4Microbiota (110). The initial focus is on Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, the University of Bonn and the University of Kassel, all of which have established links to FAIRagro and a track record of effective collaboration between their RDM centres and ZB MED and NFDI4Health on biomedical RDM training. We are also building on existing relationships with Kiel University, the Technical University of Munich, the University of Hohenheim, Humboldt University Berlin and the University of Rostock – all of which are FAIRagro participants – to develop additional training partnerships for 2025 and 2026.

Once these initial collaborations are underway, we will reach out to additional agricultural science universities and higher education institutions to expand our joint training activities.

Target group: Early-career researchers at each institution. Subject to agreement with our partners, training may also be made available to other groups, such as senior researchers and staff at infrastructure institutions. Participants come from a range of agricultural subdisciplines, depending on each university's particular areas of specialisation.

Format: In consultation with each partner, training will be delivered either online or in person, with a duration of between two hours and half a day. These sessions will provide a solid introduction to discipline-specific research data management. Alongside FAIRagro services and established structures in agrosystems research, the training will also cover

the tools and services offered by the respective institutions, with content provided by their RDM centres.

Language: English or German (as agreed with each partner).

Timeline: From 2024 to 2027, our goal is to deliver three training events per year through university partnerships.

4.1.2 Cooperation With Other Partners

Another key route for delivering FAIRagro training to the community is through the use of existing training infrastructures provided by potential partners. The de.NBI network allows training to be offered to a broad array of researchers. Other thematically related NFDI consortia – including NFDI4Earth with its Educational Hubs, NFDI4Biodiversity with its Seasonal Schools, and DataPLANT – also offer training infrastructures that FAIRagro can draw on for collaborative activities.

Collaboration on training events and the development of OER can take place on three levels:

- 1) Cross-promotion of training opportunities and OER between FAIRagro and its partners.
- 2) Integration of FAIRagro content into partners' established training formats, or vice versa.
- 3) Jointly designing and delivering training events.

Target group: Early-career researchers and senior researchers working in agrosystems research and related disciplines.

Language: English or German (as per specific requirements).

Timeline: One training event in 2023, followed by two each year from 2024 to 2026.

4.1.3 Workshops at Specialist Conferences

Short training sessions in the form of workshops will be offered at conferences organised by professional societies. These workshops will be coordinated in collaboration with M 2.1 and TA5, focusing particularly on societies that are FAIRagro participants. Key venues include the conference organised by the German Society for Crop Science (111) and the annual meeting of the German Soil Science Society (112), as well as events hosted by the German Phytomedical Society (113), the German Agricultural Research Alliance (114) and the conference of the Society for Plant Breeding (115).

Target group: Early-career researchers and senior researchers from the respective specialist fields.

Format: Workshops will be tailored to event organisers' requirements. Each session will be delivered in person and will last between one and two hours. During this time, participants will learn about the importance of FAIR research data management and receive an introduction to FAIRagro services. Participants are also encouraged to share their perspectives on FAIR RDM practices. Content will be adapted to the participants' specialist areas with support from UC staff aligned with the relevant professional society. Where possible, hands-on workshops will be offered on specific FAIRagro services, such as the Scientific Workflow Infrastructure (SciWIn).

Language: English or German, depending on the event.

Timeline: One workshop annually at specialist conferences from 2023 to 2027.

4.1.4 Training on FAIRagro Tools

Once tools and services developed by FAIRagro become available (e.g. Search Service, Legal Guidelines, Data Curation Toolbox and SciWIn), training sessions will be offered to all interested parties to help embed these services within the research community. For each service, we will provide a hands-on workshop demonstrating its functionality and application.

Target group: These sessions are designed for both early-career and senior researchers who wish to incorporate these services into their work, as well as for disseminators (staff at infrastructure institutions, educators, and data stewards) who can further disseminate these services within the community through consulting and training activities.

Format: Training will be delivered online, recorded, and made available to learners in the form of OER. Sessions will include an introduction and demonstration of the service, plus guided exercises to promote active utilisation of the tool. The sessions will be led by TA3 and TA4 staff involved in service development, supported by data stewards where applicable. They will be promoted through FAIRagro channels and cooperation partners such as de.NBI to maximise reach.

Language: English.

Timeline: One training session annually from 2024-2026, with two sessions in 2027.

4.1.5 Training on Request

We will also offer customised training programmes for self-contained groups such as research teams, projects, and institutions, tailored in response to community requests.

Sessions ranging from a few hours to half a day can be organised according to the group's needs. The *format* (online or in-person), *language* (German or English) and content will be determined in close consultation with the requesting group, with training delivered by FAIRagro staff (in collaboration with members of the group when appropriate).

Requests for bespoke training can be submitted through the FAIRagro helpdesk, through personal contact, or on the FAIRagro website.

Target group: Early-career researchers, senior researchers and/or disseminators (staff at key infrastructure institutions, educators).

Timeline: One training session in 2025 and one in 2026.

Figure 2: Timeline of FAIRagro training events

4.2 Open Educational Resources

FAIRagro will make training materials available under an open licence via the FAIRagro portal. This will be carried out in a three-step process: first, referencing and linking to existing resources from external providers; second, providing training materials from the “RDM in Agrosystems Research” training module; and, third, developing self-study materials.

4.2.1 Gathering of Existing Discipline-Specific Resources

Open educational resources will be provided to support researchers in agrosystems research in developing their research data management (RDM) skills. These OER will include materials that researchers can use independently to build their RDM competencies, as well as resources that trainers and disseminators can use to create training programmes for the research community. As a first step, relevant OER and self-study units on RDM topics will be identified through comprehensive internet searches. These resources will be systematically organised according to content, relevance to specific subdisciplines, target audience, scope, and currency. Selected resources will be described using the Research Data Alliance’s minimal metadata set (116). The compiled metadata will be published in tabular format on Zenodo and linked via the FAIRagro portal. In addition, the metadata will be adapted to the DALIA interchange format and made available for integration into the DALIA Knowledge Graph and the resource collection of the Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group of the DINI/nestor WG Research Data (117, 118).

Target group: Learners (early-career and senior researchers); educators (disseminators: staff at infrastructure institutions, university lecturers, data stewards).

Timeline: Q2 2024, update Q2 2026

4.2.2 Provision of Training Materials for Individual Events

Where possible, training materials for individual training events will be made available to participants in a two-step process (depending on the training format). Before the event, the presentation slides will be prepared by removing all the interactive slides. This pre-workshop slide set will be made available for download at the start of the training, enabling participants to take notes and try out links during the session. After the FAIRagro training, the materials used on the course will be assembled in a format that makes it easy for participants to revisit and reuse the content, specifically by making the full slide set available together with the results of exercises, discussions and group work. This post-workshop slide set may also be published if the nature of the event calls for all contributions to be published or if it is reasonable to assume there is a particular public interest in the materials.

Target group: Learners – participants in training events (early-career and senior researchers).

Timeline: 2024 to 2027

4.2.3 Provision of the Modular Training Module “RDM in Agrosystems Research”

The “RDM in Agrosystems Research” training module will be made available under an open licence. It will be designed in a way that caters to the needs of educators, that means disseminators such as data stewards, staff at infrastructure institutions, and senior researchers, allowing them to use the materials to deliver discipline-specific RDM training with minimal effort.

The full training module will be published as a master slide deck under an open licence. Alongside the slides, the package will also include all learning objectives, tasks and exercises, together with supporting materials, links and brief instructions.

The content will be structured in a modular format, giving disseminators a practical toolkit for assembling high-quality, easily accessible and audience-specific RDM training programmes from the pool of resources. Based on the DataPLANT model (71), teaching units will be provided as collections of small thematic ‘bricks’, with each brick being a self-contained building block that has its own presentation slides, worksheets, exercises and other materials. Bricks will be offered for different knowledge levels and target groups and will cover various types of content – for example, general or discipline-specific content from sub-disciplines of agrosystems research, or particular types of data. Each brick will have clear tags/labels in its slides, folder structures and metadata, making it easy to combine a selection of bricks into suitable units for different formats and target groups. An example unit for a specific target group might combine a brick introducing general principles, a brick that explores the topic in greater depth, and a brick focusing on

discipline-specific aspects. The units built from these bricks can then be combined into more elaborate teaching modules.

For each RDM topic (unit), a teaching script will be provided, outlining the timing, structure and learning objectives of an example arrangement of all the bricks relevant to that particular topic. An overarching teaching script will also be available; this will recommend ways to combine all the bricks and units into a complete training session and provide an example of the order in which the units could be tackled.

A short README file with instructions on how to use the various files will be included with the materials.

The presentation slides, exercise materials and teaching scripts will be published in various formats (pptx, pdf, odp) to make reuse easier. Plans include the release of new versions when major updates are made. Converting materials to other formats will also be explored, particularly using Liascript.

Target group: Disseminators (staff at infrastructure institutions, university lecturers, data stewards) who wish to reuse the materials.

Timeline: Q2 2025, updates from 2026 to 2027

Language: English

4.2.4 Provision of the Modular Education module “RDM in Agrosystems Research”

The “RDM in Agrosystems Research” education module described in 4.3.1 will be published under an open licence, together with the discipline-specific train-the-trainer concept also outlined in 4.3.1.

Target group: Educators working on agricultural science doctoral programmes, with data stewards and staff at infrastructure institutions as a secondary target group

Timeline: Education module: Q4 2026; train-the-trainer course: Q4 2027

4.2.5 Creation of Self-Study Materials

FAIRagro will make materials available for researchers to use for self-study purposes. These resources will be published under an open licence, enabling educators to use them in training sessions or to adapt them to create new training materials. However, the main target group for these self-study materials is learners rather than educators.

- 1) Selected online training sessions will be recorded, especially those on FAIRagro tools (see 4.1.4) and sessions with a specific thematic focus. A general introductory RDM training session will also be recorded as an example. The recordings will be

edited where necessary to ensure that only the trainers' presentations appear, not the interactive exercises. While these recordings do not offer the same level of interaction and feedback as live sessions, they are available to learners at any time and can be accessed on a flexible, as-needed basis. Additional resources for these sessions will be prepared and published as described in 4.3.2, ensuring comprehensive learning outcomes. These video recordings can also improve the reuse of published training resources by educators.

- 2) For selected topics of particular relevance to the FAIRagro community, additional open educational resources will be developed. These will serve various purposes, for example explaining and promoting tools developed by FAIRagro (e.g. the Search Service, Data Curation Toolbox or SciWin) in a clear and accessible way, or presenting content of special interest to our community. In collaboration with M 2.1, a range of formats will be developed, such as tutorial videos, short texts, FAQs, podcasts and similar resources. These will then be implemented for each tool in collaboration with the responsible parties from TA3 and TA4. The primary target group for these OER is researchers seeking information on the respective topic or tool, but the materials can also be used by educators in training sessions. Plans also include actively promoting and sharing these resources via social media channels.

Target group: Learners (early-career and senior researchers) plus educators as a secondary target group (disseminators such as staff at infrastructure institutions, university lecturers, data stewards).

Timeline: 2025 – 2027

4.2.6 Publication

FAIRagro's OER will be made discoverable in the knowledge graph of the Data Literacy Alliance (DALIA). All materials (text files, presentations, videos) will be published in the Repository for Life Sciences (FRL) under an open licence (e.g. CC BY), with a DOI assigned through the FRL. The OER – including their DOIs – will also be published on Zenodo and added to the FAIRagro community. Metadata will be adapted to the DALIA Interchange Format and made available for integration into the DALIA knowledge graph and the resource collection of the DINI/nestor Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group (117, 118). Links to the materials will also be published on the FAIRagro portal, facilitating easy access for the agricultural community through a central hub. FAIRagro's publishing policy will be adhered to, and the FAIRsFAIR checklist will be used to support FAIR creation and publication of the training materials (119).

4.3 Education

4.3.1 Educational Activities within Structured Doctoral Programmes

Early-career researchers in agrosystems research are the primary targetgroup for FAIRagro's educational initiatives. To address their needs, a dedicated education module on "RDM in Agrosystems Research" will be developed specifically for doctoral students. This module will be closely aligned with the content of the existing training module, building upon its foundation, but the two will differ in both their intended targetgroups and methodological and didactical approaches. While the training module is primarily designed for early-career researchers but remains accessible to other groups, such as senior researchers, the education module is tailored specifically for doctoral students. Its instructional design will reflect the structures and requirements of university-level teaching and is intended for integration into the curricula of structured doctoral programmes in agricultural science (see 1.4). To support this integration, a series of measures will be implemented to assist academic staff in incorporating the topic into their teaching.

- 1) To begin with, FAIRagro will offer pilot training sessions within graduate schools to gain practical experience that will feed into the development of the education module. These sessions will use the obligation to practice conscientious RDM – as part of good scientific practice – as a starting point for teaching essential RDM skills. The training will highlight general principles and connect them with discipline-specific content tailored to the participants' fields. In addition, the sessions will introduce FAIRagro's services, as well as the infrastructures and resources available at the respective institutes. In consultation with partners, ECTS credits may be awarded to incentivise participation. These pilot training sessions will be offered as part of doctoral programmes at institutions closely associated with FAIRagro, such as PhenoRob and the Graduate School Forest and Agricultural Sciences (GFA) at the University of Göttingen (75, 87).
- 2) Building on the "RDM in Agrosystems Research" training module outlined in Section 4.3.3, a dedicated education module of the same name will be developed to meet the specific requirements of graduate schools. The process will start by adapting the learning objectives matrix of the DINI/nestor Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group to align with the unique demands of agrosystems research in a doctoral student context (35). This revised matrix, combined with insights from the existing training module and established modules from agricultural science doctoral programmes – such as BIGS-LF's "Research Data Management (RDM) in Practice" module and the "Data Management with GRO.Data" module from Research Training Group 2300 "EnriCo: Enrichment of European beech forests with conifers" – will inform the development of a comprehensive training handbook for the "RDM in Agrosystems Research" education module. Staff from M 2.4 and M 2.5 will collaborate to create and publish this handbook, which will include detailed

information on learning objectives, content, instructional methods and workload (ECTS credits) (120, 121). Paired with a customised version of the master slide deck (see 4.3.3), the handbook will serve as a ready-to-use resource for academic staff at German universities and non-university doctoral programmes, enabling easy integration of discipline-specific RDM into their curricula. Like the training module, the education module will be modular in structure, allowing for flexible adaptation to different graduate school formats. Sample modules of different lengths will be created, with descriptions for module handbooks including semester load (weekly hours), example assessments and associated ECTS allocations, teaching scripts and slide decks. The education module will also indicate which general and discipline-specific aspects should be supplemented with information about institutional structures and infrastructures.

- 3) To boost teaching skills for delivering agrosystems-specific RDM training – and to make it easier to integrate the “RDM in Agrosystems Research” education module into the curriculum – the well-established train-the-trainer (TtT) concept from the FDMentor project will be adapted to the agrosystems research context (37). Didactic and conceptual elements from the FDMentor TtT model will be adopted, while subject-specific content will be delivered using the FAIRagro training module. Additionally, comprehensive guidance will be provided on effectively utilising the “RDM in Agrosystems Research” education module. Special attention will be given to adapting the module for different disciplinary and institutional settings, as well as offering information on potential collaboration partners and key contacts within institutional infrastructures.
- 4) FAIRagro will deliver the Train-the-Trainer course as a one-off event, seeking collaboration with experienced FDMentor TtT instructors from the DINI/mentor Training/Further Education Sub-Working Group and/or the federal states’ RDM initiatives. Academic staff from the doctoral programmes identified in section 1.4 will be recruited as participants, with particular emphasis on those responsible for the programmes run by FAIRagro co-applicants and participants, such as the TUM Graduate Center in Weihenstephan, the University of Hohenheim, Humboldt University Berlin, the University of Bonn, Forschungszentrum Jülich (PhenoRob), IPK, and ATB. In addition, the networks of the German Agricultural Research Alliance (DAFA) will be used to attract further potential participants.

Furthermore, the TtT workshop will also be open to data stewards and staff at infrastructure institutions in the field of agricultural sciences and related disciplines, who have frequently expressed a need for such training (39). This course will provide disseminators and data stewards with didactic training, enabling them to independently offer RDM training and educational courses for agricultural science researchers using the training resources provided by FAIRagro (see 4.3). Academic staff at universities and in doctoral programmes will gain both didactic and subject-specific skills through this course, making it easier to integrate the “RDM in Agrosystems Research” education module into higher education.

Target group: Academic staff in agricultural science doctoral programmes, with data stewards and staff at infrastructure institutions as a secondary audience

Timeline: Education module – Q4 2026; Train-the-Trainer course – Q4 2027

4.3.2 Education in the Form of Certificate Courses

Building on the content of the education module, a dedicated teaching unit will be developed that focuses exclusively on the discipline-specific aspects of agrosystems research. This unit will be created by extracting the relevant discipline-specific content from the education module and using it to expand the generic curriculum of certificate courses designed for data stewards. The agrosystems-specific learning module can be integrated into the certificate frameworks currently being developed by the RDMTraining4NFDI basic service and/or the NRW certificate course (26, 122, 123). The possibility of integrating this module into other certificate structures will also be explored.

Target group: Data stewards

Timeline: 2027

4.4 FAIRagro Portal

A dedicated training area will be created within the FAIRagro portal, serving as a central hub for all members of the agrosystems research community seeking further education in research data management. This area will fulfil three key functions:

1) *Training Calendar*

To reinforce the FAIRagro portal's status as the primary point of contact for all matters relating to RDM in agrosystems research, a training calendar will be implemented in collaboration with M 2.1. This calendar will be continuously updated and will include information on training events and educational opportunities offered by FAIRagro itself, as well as those offered by FAIRagro participants, cooperation partners and other providers relevant to the community. Training programmes offered by third parties will be regularly identified, reviewed and added to the calendar, including offerings from organisations such as NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Biodiversity, DataPLANT, de.NBI, gfbio, The Carpentries and the Helmholtz Information & Data Science Academy, as well as English-language programmes from international providers such as Elixir. All training events will be listed directly under the "Trainings" tab in the event overview. FAIRagro staff from the various co-applicants will be encouraged to enter their institutions' training events into the central FAIRagro events table so that they appear in the training calendar.

Users should be able to clearly see which training events are offered directly by FAIRagro and which are public and open to all interested parties.

The training calendar will provide the following information for each event:

- Topic/title
- Date
- Location (online/in person)
- Open to (all interested parties or specific groups, e.g. staff)
- FAIRagro training/external training
- Target group

For FAIRagro events, a registration form will be available directly on the website; for external events, a link will be provided to the registration page.

2) *Contact point* for training enquiries

3) *Access point for OER*

- a) The training area will provide links to OER from external organisations.
- b) An overview of FAIRagro OER will be available, including links and/or DOIs.
- c) The training area will also reference and link to the DALIA knowledge base and the FAIRagro resources that can be found there.

5 Outlook for the Second Funding Phase

In a potential second funding phase, FAIRagro plans to broaden both the target audiences and the formats of its training initiatives. Key considerations include:

- 1) Can the discipline-specific Train-the-Trainer course for academic staff involved in doctoral programmes and university teaching, as outlined in Section 4.2.1, be established as a permanent offering? If the course is delivered on a regular basis, it will be important to consider strategies for developing a network of graduates and creating a pool of qualified trainers. This network would support the ongoing exchange of updated training materials and foster collaboration opportunities that extend beyond the current FAIRagro funding period.
- 2) Is it possible to develop an agriculture-specific self-learning module that can be easily integrated into university teaching? To achieve this, the self-learning unit originally developed by HeFDI (see 1.2.1) would need to be revised and adapted to the specific requirements of the discipline (18). This MOOC is primarily aimed at students and is intended to make it easier for academic staff at agricultural science universities to integrate RDM into their curricula, thereby contributing to RDM education. NFDI4Biodiversity has already adapted this self-learning module to a specific discipline (see 1.3.2), and their experiences and outcomes should be drawn upon for this purpose (69). The question of whether implementation in Liascript is feasible should also be explored. This would enable the module to be provided as OER for easy reuse and adaptation and would simplify the task of

making the module available through the FAIRagro Portal for use by all interested parties.

- 3) Can scientific support staff – such as technical staff, laboratory assistants, gardeners, animal technicians, and others – be incorporated as a new target group for training and OERs? These professionals play a crucial role in practical data collection and documentation, and the quality of their work significantly influences the resulting data. However, because they typically do not engage with the data beyond their immediate tasks, they often lack awareness of the broader requirements for FAIR data management. It is therefore essential to identify what incentives could motivate this group, as they rarely benefit directly from data publication. Additionally, training materials for this audience should be provided in German and, where appropriate, use accessible, non-technical language. The need for materials and training tailored to this group has been clearly expressed at various community events, including the Community Summit 2024 and the workshop at the Bavarian State Ministry of Food, Agriculture, Forestry and Tourism in 2024.

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